

Thermodynamic Properties of Some Strong and Weak Electrolytes in Ethylene Glycol and its Aqueous Mixtures

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The thermodynamic properties of hydrogen halides and some alkali metal halides in ethylene glycol and its aqueous mixtures, as furnished by the standard potentials of Ag/AgX (X=Cl, Br, I) and M/M⁺ (M=Li, Na, K) electrodes in these media, have been reviewed. The thermodynamic quantities accompanying the transfer of these electrolytes from water to the other media as well as the corresponding values for the single ions have been analysed in the light of electrostatic and non-electrostatic effects involving solute-solvent interactions and solvent basicity. The thermodynamic quantities accompanying the acidic dissociation of some protonated amines (BH⁺) in the same media have also been discussed in terms of the individual contributions of the different species concerned.

AS a part of a comprehensive project on the studies of the properties of electrolytes in nonaqueous media, we undertook investigations on the thermodynamic behaviour of hydrogen halides and some alkali metal halides as well as some weak acids in ethylene glycol and its aqueous mixtures. The present paper summarises the relevant results in this specific area and their implications. The experimental work essentially involved the determination of the standard potentials (E°) of the Ag/AgX (X=Cl, Br, I) electrodes¹⁻⁵ and M/M⁺ (M=Li, Na, K, Cs) electrodes^{6,7} in these media, and the determination of the thermodynamic dissociation constants of some weak acids^{9, 10}.

E° of Ag/AgX electrodes. The standard potentials of the Ag/AgCl and Ag/AgBr electrodes at different temperatures (5°-45°) have been determined^{1,2} by using a cell of the type A, where X=Cl or Br.

Pt/H₂ (gas, 1atm)/HX(m), solvent/AgX-Ag ... (A)
For the Ag/AgI electrode in all the media and for the Ag/AgBr electrode in anhydrous ethylene glycol, the cell of the type A was found unsuitable, and a cell of the type B was used.^{4, 5}

Pt/H₂ (gas, 1 atm)/HOAc(m₁), NaOAc(m₂), MX(m₃),
solvent/AgX-Ag ... (B),
where X=Br or I, and M=K or Na, and HOAc denotes acetic acid. The dissociation constants of acetic acid at different temperatures in the different solvent media, required for the purpose of evaluating E° , were first determined, using the Ag/AgCl electrode in a cell of the type B. The usual method of

extrapolation was used in each case for evaluating E° .

The E_m° values (on the molar scale) so obtained at different temperatures for each medium have been fitted in the form of Harned-Robinson type equation (1) by the least square method.

$$E_m^\circ = A - B(t-25) - C(t-25)^2 \quad \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

where t denotes the temperature on the Celsius scale. The standard potentials on the mole fraction scale (E_N°) were calculated from E_m° by the relation (2).

$$E_N^\circ = E_m^\circ - 2k \log \frac{1000}{M_{xy}} \quad \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

where $k=2.3026RT/F$, and M_{xy} is the molecular weight of the pure solvent or the average molecular weight of the solvent mixture.

The standard free energy of transfer (ΔG_t°) at 25° of one mole of HX from water to another medium (ethylene glycol or its aqueous mixture) was evaluated from the E_N° values for each medium, using the E_N° value reported for water. From the temperature coefficients of the standard potentials, the standard entropy of transfer (ΔS_t°) and hence the standard enthalpy of transfer (ΔH_t°) at 25° were also evaluated, utilising the constants A, B and C of equation(1). These thermodynamic quantities are given in Table 1. The E_N° , instead of E_m° , values were used for this purpose, since a proper allowance for the scale effect is generally believed to be attainable by using the mole fraction scale.

TABLE 1—STANDARD FREE ENERGY, ENTROPY AND ENTHALPY OF TRANSFER OF HX (mole fraction scale) FROM WATER TO ETHYLENE GLYCOL-WATER MIXTURE AT 25°

Eth. glycol wt. %	$\Delta G_t^\circ(\text{HX}), \text{kcal/mole}$			$\Delta S_t^\circ(\text{HX}), \text{cal deg}^{-1} \text{mole}^{-1}$			$\Delta H_t^\circ(\text{HX}), \text{kcal/mole}$		
	HCl	HBr	HI	HCl	HBr	HI	HCl	HBr	HI
10	0.08	0.00	-0.10	-0.1	0.3	0.2	0.05	0.09	-0.04
30	0.17	0.01	-0.17	-0.3	0.0	1.0	0.08	0.01	0.12
50	0.25	0.02	-0.27	-1.1	-2.2	-2.0	-0.08	-0.64	-0.86
70	0.42	0.07	-0.43	-4.7	-6.0	-6.7	-0.98	-1.72	-2.43
90	1.20	0.70	-0.12	-8.9	-10.8	-12.6	-1.47	-2.52	-3.86
100	3.12	2.51	1.78	-7.1	-10.6	-11.5	1.00	-0.65	-1.66

E° of M/M^+ electrodes. The standard potentials of M/M^+ electrodes in ethylene glycol and its aqueous mixtures have been determined at 25°, using a cell of the type C in conjunction with a cell of the type D, the concentration of the alkali metal in the amalgam being the same in C and D.^{6,7}

The activities of the amalgams used were evaluated from the e.m.f.'s of the cell D by utilising the activities of MBr at the respective concentrations ($m_2 = 0.10, 0.20$ and 0.30) in aqueous solutions, and the standard potentials of M/M^+ and Ag-AgBr electrodes in water. These values were then used to obtain the standard e.m.f.'s (E_{cell}°)_E of the cell E,

where $X = \text{Br}$ in this particular case. The E° values for the Ag-AgBr electrode in the different media being already known, the standard potentials of the M/M^+ electrodes were thus evaluated.

By coupling the E° values of the M/M^+ electrodes with those of the Ag-AgCl and Ag-AgI electrodes determined earlier, the values of (E_{cell}°)_E were obtained for $X = \text{Cl}$ and I , for all the media. The values of (E_{cell}°)_E on the mole fraction scale, obtained from those on the molar scale by the usual method, were utilised to evaluate the standard free energies of transfer, $\Delta G_t^\circ(\text{MX})$, of the different alkali halides (MX) from water to glycol and its

aqueous mixtures at 25°. These $\Delta G_t^\circ(\text{MX})$ values are shown in Table 2.

Thermodynamic dissociation constants of acids. A cell of the type F has been used to determine the acidic dissociation constants of ammonium and

 TABLE 2—STANDARD FREE ENERGY OF TRANSFER $\Delta G_t^\circ(\text{MX})$, OF SOME ELECTROLYTES (MX) FROM WATER TO AQUO-GLYCOLIC SOLVENTS IN KCAL/MOLE AT 25° (mole fraction scale)

Wt. % Glycol	30	50	70	90	100
LiCl	0.37	0.65	1.13	1.64	1.91
NaCl	0.32	0.58	0.85	1.13	1.43
KCl	0.37	0.62	0.97	1.18	1.43
CsCl	—	0.62	—	—	1.48
LiBr	0.21	0.42	0.78	1.15	1.31
NaBr	0.16	0.35	0.51	0.65	0.83
KBr	0.21	0.39	0.62	0.69	0.83
CsBr	—	0.39	—	—	0.88
LiI	0.05	0.14	0.30	0.35	0.60
NaI	0.00	0.07	0.02	-0.16	0.12
KI	0.05	0.12	0.14	-0.12	0.12
CsI	—	0.11	—	—	0.16

several alkyl-substituted ammonium ions in ethylene glycol at nine temperatures (5°-45°)⁹.

Pt/H₂ (gas, 1 atm)/BH⁺ Br(m₁), B(m₂),
solvent/AgBr-Ag(F),
where B is ammonia or an amine.

The pK_{BH⁺} values at different temperatures were fitted into a Harned-Robinson type equation(2) by the method of least squares.

$$pK_{BH^+} = a/T + b + cT \quad \dots\dots\dots(2),$$

and the standard thermodynamic quantities, ΔG° , ΔH° , ΔS° and ΔC_p° , for the dissociation of the acids in ethylene glycol have been evaluated from the constants of equation (2).

The acid dissociation constants of protonated Tris(hydroxymethyl)-methyl amine have been determined¹⁰ at 25° in aqueous mixtures of ethylene glycol, using a cell of the type F. The corresponding values for protonated *p*-nitroaniline were determined spectrophotometrically¹⁰. As the electrostatic effect on the acid dissociation of protonated amines should be small, the thermodynamic quantities associated with the process are expected to furnish useful information regarding the nature of specific solute-solvent interaction. For ascertaining the probable contributions of the uncharged species(B) taking part in the equilibria, solubilities of the amines in these solvents were measured to evaluate the medium effects.

For an understanding of the protolytic equilibria in ethylene glycol and its aqueous mixtures, the autoprotolysis constants of these media were determined at different temperatures, and the relevant thermodynamic quantities were also evaluated.^{11,12}

Solvent effects on the thermodynamic properties of hydrogen halides and alkali halides. Attempts have been made to analyse the thermodynamic quantities obtained from the above studies in the light of solute-solvent and solvent-solvent interactions^{5,6}.

The ΔG_i° (HX) values in Table 1 show that for HCl and HBr, the transfer from water to the mixed media is non-spontaneous, becoming more unfavourable as the proportion of glycol increases. For HI, however, ΔG_i° has negative values, and attaining a minimum around 80% glycol, ultimately goes over to positive values in the extreme glycol-rich region. In any particular medium, the ease of transfer of the three hydrogen halides lies in the order : HI > HBr >

HCl. The hydrogen ion being common to all these electrolytes, this gives the order for the ease of transfer of halide ions from water to any particular glycolic medium as : I⁻ > Br⁻ > Cl⁻. From Table 2 it may be seen that the standard free energy of transfer of the alkali chlorides and bromides is positive in each case, indicating that their transfer from water to ethylene glycol or its aqueous mixtures is thermodynamically unfavourable. The behaviour of NaI and KI is rather anomalous, recalling that of HI in this respect. For any particular alkali metal, however, the ease of transfer lies in the order : I⁻ > Br⁻ > Cl⁻, the same as for the hydrogen halides.

Attempts have been made to utilise the ΔG_i° (HX) values for evaluating the standard free energies of transfer of the individual ions, ΔG_i° (i), by a method of extrapolation⁴⁻⁶ essentially based on Born equation, the conceptual approach being similar to those of Izmailov et al^{13,14} and Feakins et al¹⁵⁻¹⁷. The plots of ΔG_i° (HX) and of ΔG_i° (HCl-HX) against $(r_X^-)^{-1}$ were simultaneously extrapolated to $(r_X^-)^{-1}=0$, and the values of ΔG_i° (H⁺) and ΔG_i° (Cl⁻) were obtained. Using these values for each solvent, the values of ΔG_i° (i) for all the other halide ions were calculated, as shown in Table 4.

The electrostatic contributions ($\Delta G_{i,el}^\circ$) to these ΔG_i° (i) values for the M⁺ and X⁻ ions have been calculated with the help of Born equation, taking the radii equal to the respective crystallographic radii of the ions, and hence the "chemical" part ($\Delta G_{i,ch}^\circ$) has been evaluated in each case by subtracting $\Delta G_{i,el}^\circ$ from ΔG_i° (i). These values are also in Table 4. Because of the uncertainty in the radius of the hydrogen ion in different media, no attempt was made to split up ΔG_i° (H⁺) into the electrostatic and chemical components. From Table 4 it may be seen that the transfer of hydrogen ion is spontaneous for all the media, being most favourable for the medium containing about 90% glycol. The electrostatic contribution to ΔG_i° (H⁺) should be positive for each medium since the dielectric constant is lower than that of water, and hence $\Delta G_{i,ch}^\circ$ is expected to be still more negative.

It will be found that the free energy of transfer for all the cations (including hydrogen ion) are negative for all the solvent media, becoming increasingly negative as the proportion of glycol in the mixed solvent increases. On the other hand, ΔG_i° (i) for each of the three halide ions is positive, increasing in magnitude with the increase in the content of glycol in the medium. Thus, the transfer of cations from

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TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC QUANTITIES FOR THE DISSOCIATION OF MONOPOSITIVE CATIONIC ACIDS IN GLYCOL AT 25°.

	ΔG° (kcal. mole ⁻¹)	ΔH° (kcal. mole ⁻¹)	ΔS° (cal. mole ⁻¹ deg. ⁻¹)	ΔC_p° (cal. mole ⁻¹ deg. ⁻¹)
Ammonium	15.47	16.29	+2.7	+ 6
Methylammonium	16.74	16.45	-1.0	- 6
Dimethylammonium	16.49	15.25	-4.1	-11
Trimethylammonium	14.90	13.17	-5.8	-13
Ethylammonium	16.57	16.16	-1.4	- 2
Diethylammonium	16.42	15.34	-3.6	- 5
Triethylammonium	15.62	13.41	-7.4	- 9
Monoethanolammonium	15.47	15.27	-0.7	-19
Diethanolammonium	14.26	13.42	-2.8	-15
Triethanolammonium	13.05	11.54	-5.1	-14
Protonated tris	14.30	14.53	+0.8	+ 2

 TABLE 4— ΔG_t° (i) AND $\Delta G_{t, ch}^\circ$ (i) OF SOME INDIVIDUAL IONS IN KCAL/G-ION FROM WATER TO AQUO-GLYCOLIC MEDIA AT 25° (mole fraction scale)

Wt. % Glycol	ΔG_t° (i)					$\Delta G_{t, ch}^\circ$ (i)				
	30	50	70	90	100	30	50	70	90	100
H ⁺	-1.73	-2.49	-4.22	-5.30	-4.37					
Li ⁺	-1.53	-2.09	-3.51	-5.86	-5.58	-1.94	-2.90	-5.00	-7.60	-9.30
Na ⁺	-1.58	-2.16	-3.79	-5.37	-6.06	-1.84	-2.68	-4.74	-7.11	-8.42
K ⁺	-1.53	-2.12	-3.67	-5.32	-6.06	-1.72	-2.49	-4.35	-6.57	-7.76
Cl ⁻	1.90	2.74	4.64	6.50	7.49	1.76	2.46	4.13	5.56	6.21
Br ⁻	1.74	2.51	4.29	6.00	6.88	1.61	2.26	3.82	5.15	5.72
I ⁻	1.57	2.24	3.81	5.20	6.16	1.44	2.01	3.39	4.43	5.13

water is increasingly spontaneous, whereas the transfer of anions is increasingly non-spontaneous. In other words, anions are hydrophilic, but cations are glycophilic. If ΔG_t° (H⁺) be taken as an index of affinity for hydrogen ion, relative to that for water,

glycol is found to be more protophilic, i.e. basic, than water. The basicity of the mixed media increases with the increase in the proportion of glycol and apparently reaches a maximum around 90% glycol. The absence of a monotonic increase

in basicity beyond this point may arise from structural factors, combined with the electrostatic effect.

The solvation of the charged species is expected to be largely determined by the charge density of the positive and negative charge centres of the isolated solvent dipoles. The protonic character and hence the charge intensity on the hydrogen atom of the hydroxyl group in glycol appear to be smaller than that in water, whereas the negative charge intensity on the oxygen atom is somewhat larger than in water dipole. Hence, glycol has a larger solvating capacity for cations, but smaller for anions, than water. It may be of interest to note in this context that from a similar analysis of the standard potential data for methanol-water solvent system as reported in the literature,¹⁹ as well as our own data for the propylene glycol methanol solvent system^{12, 19-22} it appears that the 'basicity' of the solvents lies in the order :

Methanol > propylene glycol > ethylene glycol > water.

The ΔS_i° (HX) values of the hydrogen halides were also split up, as for ΔG_i° (HX), into the standard entropies, $\Delta S_i^\circ(i)$, for the transfer of individual ions by extrapolation, and hence $\Delta H_i^\circ(i)$ values were also evaluated. The electrostatic contributions ($\Delta S_{i,el}^\circ$) to the values of $\Delta S_i^\circ(X^-)$ for the halide ions have been calculated using the differential form of Born equation, and hence the 'chemical' contributions ($\Delta S_{i,ch}^\circ$) have been evaluated by subtracting $\Delta S_{i,el}^\circ$ from $\Delta S_i^\circ(X^-)$. Combining the values of $\Delta G_{i,ch}^\circ$ and $\Delta S_{i,ch}^\circ$ the respective values of $\Delta H_{i,ch}^\circ$ for the halide ions have been obtained. All these values are given in the Table 5.

It is found that the general trend in the variations in the values of $\Delta S_i^\circ(i)$ as well as $\Delta H_i^\circ(i)$ for any halide ion is opposite to that for hydrogen ion. The values for the halide ions are negative at lower proportions of glycol, but become increasingly positive as the percentage of glycol increases. The reverse is the case with hydrogen ion. Structural factors are obviously reflected in the entropy values. The observed results further substantiate that halide ions are preferentially solvated by water, whereas glycol exhibits higher solvating capacity towards hydrogen ion. The results further tend to suggest that in the early stages of addition of glycol to water, no promotion of enhanced structure occurs in water, as happens on the addition of monohydric alcohols.²³⁻²⁵ On

further addition, however, glycol causes breakdown of water structure like other alcohols.

Solvent effects on proton transfer equilibria

The ΔG° values for the acidic dissociation of the different substituted ammonium ions in ethylene glycol (Table 3) indicate that the acid strengths for the methyl-, ethyl- and hydroxyethyl- substituted species consistently lie in the order: primary < secondary < tertiary. It is known that in aqueous solutions no unique order is found for all the series. The observed results indicate that, besides the inductive effect, the solvation effect in glycol is predominant, since the methyl and ethyl groups are solvophilic towards glycol, whereas they behave as solvophobic towards water. As solvation is expected largely to affect the entropies of the respective species involved in the dissociation process, a better insight into the solute-solvent interaction is likely to be obtainable from the ΔS° values. These values also suggest that solvation plays the dominant role in the dissociation equilibria of the substituted ammonium ions in ethylene glycol. The results further tend to substantiate that there is no characteristic structure in glycol, as in water, although a high degree of association due to hydrogen bonding may well be present in glycol. The same conclusion has also been arrived at from an analysis of the thermodynamic quantities associated with the self-ionisation of glycol.¹²

The understanding of the solvent effect on the proton transfer equilibria involving a conjugate acid-base pair A and B become easier if we consider the free energy change, $\Delta G_{[A-B]}^\circ$, accompanying the transfer process (3) from a reference solvent S_o (water in the present case) to any other solvent S (glycol or its aqueous mixture)¹⁰.

where (s) and (s_o) denote the standard states in any solvent S and the reference solvent S_o(water) respectively. In our present case, the acid A is the protonated amine (BH⁺) and B the free amine. The standard free energy change for the transfer process (3) for the [BH⁺—B] system is given by equation (4).

$$\Delta G_i^\circ [BH^+—B]_{sys} = 2.303RT[p(K)_s - p(K)_{s_o}] = \Delta G_i^\circ(H^+) + \Delta G_i^\circ(B) - \Delta G_i^\circ(BH^+) \quad (4)$$

where K denotes the dissociation constants (on mole fraction scale) of the acid BH⁺ in the respective

TABLE 5—THERMODYNAMIC QUANTITIES (mole fraction scale) FOR TRANSFER OF INDIVIDUAL IONS FROM WATER TO ETHYLENE-GLYCOL WATER MIXTURES AT 25°

Ion	$\Delta S_i^\circ(i)$ cal deg ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹	$\Delta S_{1,cb}^\circ(i)$ cal deg ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹	$\Delta H_i^\circ(i)$ kcal/mole	$\Delta H_{1,cb}^\circ(i)$ kcal/mole
<i>30 wt. % Glycol</i>				
H ⁺	6.8	—	0.28	—
Cl ⁻	-7.1	-5.9	-0.20	0.02
Br ⁻	-6.8	-5.7	-0.27	0.03
I ⁻	-5.8	-4.8	-0.16	0.04
<i>70 wt. % Glycol</i>				
H ⁺	-17.8	—	-9.52	—
Cl ⁻	13.0	16.9	8.51	9.16
Br ⁻	11.8	15.4	7.80	8.40
I ⁻	11.1	14.5	7.09	7.62
<i>90 wt. % Glycol</i>				
H ⁺	-32.0	—	-14.85	—
Cl ⁻	23.0	28.6	13.36	14.11
Br ⁻	21.2	26.4	12.50	13.01
I ⁻	19.4	24.1	10.99	11.84
<i>100 wt. % Glycol</i>				
H ⁺	-38.6	—	-15.86	—
Cl ⁻	31.5	38.5	16.85	17.66
Br ⁻	28.0	34.5	15.22	16.06
I ⁻	27.1	33.0	14.20	14.92

solvents. Here, $\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{H}^+)$ can be identified as the standard free energy change for the process(5).

By equation(4), $\Delta G_i^\circ[\text{BH}^+ - \text{B}]_{\text{sys}}$ can be obtained from the pK values, and hence $\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{BH}^+)$ evaluated by using the $\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{H}^+)$ given in Table 3 and $\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{B})$ obtained from solubility measurements of the free amines in the different solvents. The relevant results are in Table 6 for the two systems.

The values of $\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{BH}^+ - \text{B})_{\text{sys}}$ for both the amines are found to pass through minima with gradual addition of glycol. This is a common feature in aqueous mixtures of organic solvents, and has been ascribed to increased basicity of the mixed media caused by the breakdown of water structure.^{2, 24, 26, 27} The contributions of the uncharged species, $\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{B})$ have often been ignored, but Table 6 shows that this is an important factor. The positive values of $\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{B})$ for tris indicate that this base is more hydrophilic than glycolphilic, possibly because of the

TABLE 6—SOLVENT EFFECTS ON DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF PROTONATED TRIS AND *p*-NITROANILINE IN ETHYLENE GLYCOL-WATER SOLVENT SYSTEM AT 25° (mole fraction scale). VALUES ARE IN CAL MOLE⁻¹.

Wt. % glycol	Tris			<i>p</i> -Nitroaniline		
	$\Delta G_i^\circ[\text{BH}^+-\text{B}]_{\text{sys}}$	$\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{B})$	$\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{BH}^+)$	$\Delta G_i^\circ[\text{BH}^+-\text{B}]_{\text{sys}}$	$\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{B})$	$\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{BH}^+)$
10	35	39	—	—98	—211	—
30	—7	98	—1630	—359	—628	—2000
50	—30	150	—2310	—675	—1203	—3030
70	48	216	—4050	—925	—1873	—5170
90	690	335	—5660	—739	—2822	—7380
100	2545	368	—6550	713	—3318	—8400

presence of three hydroxy-groups in the molecule. The large negative values of $\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{B})$ for *p*-nitroaniline indicate that it has a much greater affinity for glycol than for water possibly because of the presence of the hydrophobic benzene ring. Other factors may also have their contributions.¹⁰ Regarding $\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{BH}^+)$, Table 6 shows that for both the protonated amines, these values are negative, indicating that the transfer of either of the BH^+ ions from water is spontaneous, becoming more so with increasing proportion of glycol, as in the case of other cations (Table 4). This further substantiates the higher solvating capacity of glycol towards positively charged species by virtue of the higher negative charge intensity on the oxygen atom in the hydroxy-group in the glycol molecule. The overall behaviour of the protonated amines thus appears to be largely dictated by specific solute-solvent interactions as well as the solvent 'basicity' as reflected in the $\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{H}^+)$ values.

Concluding remarks. Much of the above discussions may be open to serious objections. The very concept of thermodynamic quantities for single ions is based on extra-thermodynamic considerations. Even if these values be assumed to have real thermodynamic significance, one may feel sceptic about the extrapolation method used for evaluating them. In fact, different methods of extrapolation have been suggested^{7, 24, 28-31} and the different approaches have yielded values which differ not only in magnitude but also sometimes in sign.²⁴ Moreover, it seems doubtful whether $\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{H}^+)$ can be strictly considered as a true measure of relative proton affinity or 'basicity'^{24, 32}, as postulated in the preceding sections,

Nevertheless, the general trend in the variations of the thermodynamic quantities as discussed above may reasonably be accepted as something real, although one may feel reluctant to attach much importance to the absolute magnitudes.

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